

Cognitive Behavior Therapy: Lived Experience of Patients with Major Depressive Disorder

Mobushira Zainab, Syeda Shahida Batool, Bareera Saeed, Hadiyyatur Rahman Mubarak, Mamoonah Khan

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 14, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 16, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Cognitive Behavior Therapy, Major Depressive Disorder, Lived Experiences, IPA.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5787418</p>	<p><i>Cognitive behavior therapy is used massively as a countermeasure for major depressive disorder. The current study aimed to explore the experiences of patients with major depressive disorder who were going through Cognitive Behavior Therapy. The interviews were taken from 10 male and female patients with major depressive disorder of age between 20 to 40 years. Data were analyzed by using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis. Analysis of the verbatim yielded 4 superordinate themes providing an over view of the lived experience of patient with major depressive disorder. The superordinate themes obtained by depth analysis were; pretherapeutic phase, initial effects of cognitive behavior therapy, middle therapeutic phase, perceived effective and ineffective techniques. Results of the study provide comprehensive over view of the lived experience of patients with major depressive disorder, who were undergoing cognitive behavior therapy.</i></p>

Introduction

Cognitive behavior therapy (CBT) is a form of psychotherapy that aims to help patients understand how their ideas and feelings affect their behaviors. Cognitive behavior therapy is commonly used to treat a variety of problems (e.g., phobias, addictions, anxiety, and, most importantly, and sadness). It helps patients to deal with specific problem by finding out various ways of solution to certain difficulties. Through CBT, patients learn how to identify the problematic behavior and change the destructive and disturbing irrational thoughts that cause negative influence on behavior and emotions into rational beliefs. The main goal of CBT is to teach patients that they cannot control all aspects of life. They can only regulate the way they interpret and deal with the things that are around them in their environment (da Silva et al., 2018).

Extensive empirical evidences support the cognitive behavior therapy as an efficacious intervention for the treatment of acute major depressive disorder and prevention of depressive relapse. The most significant role of cognitive behavior therapy is to accentuate on identifying and cultivating individual strength and to modify the thought pattern of the patients of major depressive disorder. CBT however, enhance the efficacy of patient's thought pattern and as well as clarify the process that mediates it salubrious effects (Purehsan&Saed, 2010). Risk of depression in younger age is appeared to be steadily increasing, and CBT helps to manage and cure the patients with major depressive disorder. (Soetrisno et al., 2017). Indeed, increased public awareness of depression's devastating personal and financial consequences has aided in catalyzing a burgeoning research effort in recent decades to identify effective acute and prophylactic psychological interventions for this disorder, with Aron's Beck's (1967) cognitive behavior therapy, being by far the most extensively researched of these. He proposed this therapy under the cognitive school of thought.

Cognitive behavior therapy is a common type of talk therapy that sometimes works better than medication to treat depression. It works more efficiently, if cognitive behavior therapy is combined with any antidepressant or other drugs. A therapist, first identifies incorrect and negative thoughts after recognizing them he tends to replace those false beliefs with positive, healthier and more realistic considerations. One might consider oneself as less worthy and resplendent with flaws, however, CBT aids to deal with shortcomings and flaws by teaching the patient to swap negative thoughts with more positive ones. Behavior get changed once attitude of the patient is modified. That can help to ease the depression (Kenardy et al., 2005).

One of the constructive point of CBT is that it involves patient in the treatment. They actively participate by identifying distorted perception, recognizing negative thought and find out evidence supporting negative and alternative beliefs. It also helps to produce rational, believable and more accurate thoughts and this process is called cognitive restructuring. Negative thoughts are reformed and reconstruct into progressive beliefs. CBT is occurred in three phases with the purpose of curing depression. First phase is to focus on automatic thought and

on depressogenic cognitive style. Second phase is to concentrate on the way one relates to other, and the last phase is behavioral modification which enables individual to solve his/her problem. The general assumptions of CBT are that abnormality is erroneous cognitions about others, about World and even about one's own self. This faulty cognition is a result of cognitive paucity, lack of planning, cognitive distortion and inadequately processing the facts and figures. Aaron Beck proposed the cognitive triad (i.e., cognition causes distortion in the manner we assume things. Another assumption is we see world through our mental representation. If such depiction is working inappropriately it will cause inadequate emotion along with disordered behavior (Ghaderi, 2009).

Major Depressive Disorder

Depression, often known as major depressive disorder or clinical depression, is a significant mood disease that affects millions of people. Patients with severe depressive illness have persistent feelings of despair, sorrow, and a lack of interest and pleasure in nearly all previously liked activities. Patients may also suffer from physical illnesses such as chronic pain or digestive difficulties, in addition to mental concerns. These symptoms should be present for at least 2 weeks only, then it will fulfill the criteria of major depressive disorder. Depression is the most expensive and enervating ailment worldwide and it causes the substantial impairment of both occupational life and as well as social functioning, and the well-known way to treat depression is cognitive behavior therapy. Undoubtedly, CBT is an operative treatment to cure depression, but most of the time, clients do not complete their CBT session. According to them, they experience difficulty in understanding the CBT techniques. Subsequently, after receiving one to two sessions they tend to withdraw. From the study, it was found that in order to enhance the effectiveness of CBT, there is need to highlight the possible barriers between CBT and client. Clinicians can help clients to make better choice regarding therapy. In this way clients can be benefited from the therapy by learning different skills that enable them to successfully deal with depression. After knowing the experiences of patients, it was concluded that clinicians should bring further development in their CBT techniques i.e., (I) they should negotiate with the participants about the challenges of CBT, such as homework. (II) Exploring the possible barriers while conducting the therapy that may engage the client and help in the completion of therapy. (III) Clients must report the benefits of CBT, which of the learning strategy help them the most in identifying negative thought pattern and enable them to deal with their depression (Kessler, 2012).

CBT is comprised of fewer sessions as compared to the other therapies. Clients experienced changes in themselves after receiving the CBT. According to the clients, it helped them in managing their depression, prevent them from relapsing. Patients learned different skills to cope up with stressful life situations and they also learned to manage their emotions. Due to depression, patients may face difficulty in managing their relations. CBT makes the client capable enough to resolve the relationship conflicts and learned better way of communication. Clients may experience risk because of CBT, because clients explore their painful feelings, experiences and emotions. They may cry, get upset or feel the emotion of anger during a challenging session. They may also feel physically drained. Sometimes CBT confront the situation that patient would rather avoid. However, skilled therapist will minimize any risk and coping skills help patients to manage and conquer negative feelings and fears (Weitkamp et al., 2016).

Application of CBT in Pakistan

CBT is rarely is practiced in non-western countries or developing countries that includes Pakistan. There might be possibility of the effectiveness of CBT while treating mental health problems in developing countries such major depressive disorder. The major reason for the application of CBT in developing countries are the medicine for the treatment of depression are much costly. As the cost of medicine in these third world countries are comparatively higher than the western countries and there are less human resources available, therefore, treatment of depression with additional therapeutic technique is moderately difficult for these patients. There is a need of cultural adaptation before applying it in the patients of non-western culture, modification in therapy must be done by keeping cultural and religious factors under the consideration, because in Pakistan psychologists tend to use CBT with religious practices as part of therapeutic intervention. Other problems which could be raised in these undeveloped countries regarding cognitive behavior therapy are: (I) psychologists do not aware families properly and do not ask them for their role in treating the patients. They should be aware of the session or part of the session that is essential for them to know. Even patients should be aware of the whole process. (II) Secondly, inadequate therapeutic techniques which need to be modified according to the culture. Pakistani people are more likely to prefer seeking help from faith healers, as compared to people of developed countries. There is a need of number of adjustments to make CBT acceptable, accessible and effective. However, for the adjustment of CBT in Pakistan, there is a need of trained psychologists, vital expertise and resources that might not be readily available in the under developed countries (Yousaf et al., 2020).

Literature Review

Depression has a major influence on patients' and their families' lives, negatively impacting their social and vocational lives as well as creating other functional deficits. The purpose of this study is to describe and analyze

the perception of cognitive behavior therapy in patients with major depressive illness, as well as the techniques employed and the success of this therapeutic strategy. To summarize, CBT is one of the therapy options for depression that has the most scientific proof of success. A study was conducted to understand the use of cognitive behavior therapy and to examine its efficacy in the treatment of Major Depressive Disorder. CBT was given along with pharmacological therapy. The data were collected through meta-analyses of non-systematic review of the literature of actual study and rest of the data were collected from specialized textbooks. The result of the study indicates that CBT is one of the therapeutic modality that treats depression with the highest empirical evidence of efficacy. Whether CBT is given alone or CBT is given in combination with some other pharmacotherapy (Jalal et al., 2017). Those individuals who used injections and drugs, they suffered HIV which caused depression and distress that could interfere in personal life and as well as with their critical self-care behavior and such depression may lead to Major Depressive Disorder. The study shows the feasibility of CBT which is applied to improve adherence and depression among individuals who are suffering from depression, and living the entirely low life in despair. This misery is because they are patients of HIV. The outcome of the results shows that treatment through cognitive behavior therapy is achievable and acceptable which helps the patients in reducing their depression and also aid to improve their self-care behavior in the manner of extremely complicated and complex medical and psychiatry comorbidity (Sachsenweger et al., 2015).

One of the study stated that mostly, a time comes when an antidepressant failed to respond for the cure of their depression. At that moment there is need of an additional treatment that could be cognitive behavior therapy. The aim of this pair is to describe the study protocol for a randomized control trail that measures the clinical effectiveness of CBT. Patients aged 20-65 were selected as a sample. They were diagnosed with major depressive disorder. Those patients were taken as a sample who were failed to response to antidepressant and they were assigned to receive the CBT along with their usual treatment. Results of the study showed that quality of life stepped up by applying CBT on patients. They responded to it more efficiently than any other treatments (Sidman, 2017).

According to another study, there is a lack of empirical support for cognitive behavior therapy in treating Japanese patients with severe depressive illness, thus a feasibility study of CBT in Japanese clinical settings is urgently needed. Patients aged 18 to 60 years old who satisfied the criteria for a primary diagnosis of current major depressive disorder were included in the study. CBT for patients with severe depressive disorder appears to be practical and may result in positive treatment results in Japanese patients with major depression (Warner et al., 2011).

Four participants in an alcohol use disorder treatment setting received cognitive-behavioral therapy for depression as part of their treatment. To discover important themes, semi-structured interviews with participants were subjected to interpretive phenomenological analysis. Peer support, changed thinking habits, improved levels of confidence, and self-efficacy were all mentioned as advantages of the group experience. Because of the advantages reported by the participants, this study shows that depression management, especially in a group format, should be given more frequently as an integrated element of alcohol therapy. The cobalt trail aimed to examine the effectiveness of CBT along with the pharmacotherapy for the treatment of the patients with major depressive disorder, instead of using the pharmacotherapy alone. There were two parallel groups which were recruited, total number of participants were 469. Their age was between 18-75 and they were selected through randomized controlled trail. These 46 patients were divided into two groups. One group received the antidepressant and the other group received the antidepressant along with CBT. After analysis, it was found that CBT was an additional care technique, which is added to usual care that includes antidepressant as an operational care, which helps to reduce depressive symptoms in population (Gold, 2015). A study portrayed the experiences of patients with major depressive disorder went through cognitive behavior therapy. This study showed how the patients found CBT difficult in curing their disorder. According to these clients they withdrew the session because they did not find it effective against their depression. Purposive sampling was done in order to collect the data. 74 patients withdrew the session and out of 74 only 54 patients gave the reason for stopping or for not starting the CBT. Qualitative analysis was applied to find out the results. Results showed that client struggle in and between the sessions. CBT homework was the biggest challenge for them but those who attended more than one session claimed that they had gained insight into managing their depression and CBT homework enabled them to replace their negative thoughts with positive thoughts (Zagorski, 2019).

A study retrospectively examined the outcome in 88 patients of depression out of 143, who were going through CBT. Depression was measured through Beck Depression Inventory (BDI II). The result show that if CBT is given to patients in routine care settings for the treatment of depression, it would have good results in term of both improvement in clinical setting at individual level and as well as progress was seen at group level too. However, there were still number of patients who did not get any benefit from this therapy due to various reasons. And most of them dropped out of the treatment as they did not find it working (Lebedev et al., 2021).

A study was conducted to emphasize on major depressive disorder and inadequate self-care. The aim of the study was to determine the efficacy of CBT for the treatment of patients with major depressive disorder. Data of 158 patients was selected through random selection. Statistical analysis were applied to check the efficacy of

CBT on depression patients. From the conclusion it was found that patients experienced the CBT more competently that not only reduced the symptoms of major depressive disorder but also it lessened the anxiety symptoms, improved social function and made the life healthy (Stefan & Hofmann, 2019).The frequency of depression among young individuals is high in this study, and the potential harmful consequences are considerable.

The importance of timely evidence-based therapy cannot be overstated. Cognitive behavior therapy is currently recommended as a first-line treatment for depression; nevertheless, the amount to which CBT improves depressive symptoms differs among research. To categorize the description of CBT intervention, a constant comparative technique was utilized. Overall, reporting of CBT protocols was highly favorable for patients, according to the findings (Li et al., 2016).

Another study was conducted to explore the experience of depression and as well as experience of therapy that was provided to the patients with major depressive disorder. Semi-structured interviews were conducted from 5 young patients. Their age range was between 15 to 19 year. Analysis was done by using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis. Themes were identified from the studywere: (I) suffering is experienced as overwhelming. (II) An experience of loneliness and isolation. (III) Struggling to understand the suffering, (IV) CBT as a last resort. The findings suggest that including all the treatment in order to cure depression, the patients experienced the CBT as the most effective treatment (Zauderer, 2012).

Studies have shown that the treatment of major depressive disorder with antidepressants was lesser effective than the treatment that includes antidepressant along with CBT and it becomes even more impactful when group CBT is provided to the patients of major depressive disorder. In a study, sample of 62 patients were randomized into 2 groups, and 30 were added into control group, who received only drugs for their disorder. Rest of 32 patients were put into experimental group and they were provided with both drugs and CBT. For the evaluation, Hamilton Depression Rating scale, Hamilton Anxiety Rating scale, Life Satisfaction Rating were applied to assess participants after 12 weeks of treatment and at the end of one year of follow up. Results disclosed that depressive symptoms of both groups were improved significantly. But there was more improvement in the experimental group and this is that group which received both drugs and as well as CBT. It enhanced their social functioning and quality of life and made the life healthier (Kotianova et al., 2015).

Rationale and Objective of Study

The core purpose of this study is to explore the lived experiences of patients with Major Depressive Disorder, who were undergoing the cognitive behavior therapy. Most of the past researches were interested in identifying the effect of cognitive behavior therapy on the symptoms of Major Depressive Disorder. Few were interested in knowing the lived experiences of patients with depression. Some of the previous researches report the experience of depression and as well as experience of therapy that was provided to the patients of depression was found much promising (Weitkamp et al., 2016). Some of the researches claimed that there should be culturally adapt CBT for patients of depression. So, this study intended to explore the experiences of patients with major depressive disorder going through Cognitive behavior therapy.

Research Question

What are the lived experiences of patients with Major Depressive Disorder who are under going Cognitive behavior therapy?

Method

Research Design

Qualitative design was used in this current study to explore the lived experiences of clients of major depression going through CBT. A qualitative research design allows exploring experiences through open ended semi structure questions. The data gathered were analyzed by using Interpretative phenomenological analysis because it is considered to be the best analysis technique for exploring the lived experiences.

Sample

Sample was selected thorough a purposive sampling. A sample of ten participants, who were suffering from major depressive disorder was taken from hospitals. The patients who had received at least five sessions of CBT out of eight were included in the study, so that the clients who had adequate experience of CBT could be interviewed.

Table 1: *Demographic Characteristics of the Sample (N = 10)*

Participant	Age	Gender	Session
1	35	Male	5 th
2	24	Female	5 th
3	22	Female	6 th
4	26	Male	5 th
5	24	Female	5 th
6	36	Male	5 th
7	38	Female	5 th

8	26	Male	5 th
9	29	Female	5 th
10	40	Male	6 th

Table 1 shows that demographics of the participants.

Instrument

Semi structured interview schedule was developed to collect data about the experiences of patients of major depressive disorder, who were receiving CBT. The semi structured interview schedule consisted of questions covered the perception of patients regarding biological, behavioral, professional and social changes due to CBT as a treatment. The interview schedule consisted of 20 questions regarding experiences of patients of major depressive disorder.

Procedure

First of all, the topic of the thesis was approved by the board of studies of the department of Psychology of the university. The data were collected from different hospitals. Informed consent was taken from the participant and they were informed about the study before interview was taken from them. A semi structured interview was conducted with each participant under the supervision of their therapists. Interview continued for about 30 to 35 minutes. After an interview, verbatim of each participant was transcribed. The transcription was translated and translation was read and reread in order to gain the understanding of verbatim. The data were analyzed using principles of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis, proposed by Smith and Osborn in 2008.

Results and Discussion

The IPA principles were used for verbatim analysis. In each example, the analysis revealed a slew of themes. Both similar and dissimilar themes were grouped together under key topics. The major themes of each case were established in order to have a deeper understanding of the participants' experiences. After building primary themes tables for each instance, the master table was created. The master table included all of the topics that were present in all of the instances. During the analysis, a master table was discovered that contains experiences of patients with major depressive illness who were receiving cognitive behavior therapy.

Table 2: Master table of all interviews (N=10)

Super ordinate Themes	Subordinate themes	Emergent Themes
1. Pre-therapeutic phase	Cognitions	— Negative thought process — Loss of pleasure — Excessive anxious thoughts — Excessive mental pressure — Hopelessness — Excessive fear — Excessive feelings of regret — Disappointment from life — Remained silent — Rigidity — Abusive language — Agitation
	Behavioral	— Excessive crying — Self-induced isolation — Inability to perform tasks — Disinterest in house hold — Excessive physical weakness — Insomnia
	Biological	— Loss of appetite — Constant headache — Obesity due to depression — Chills and sweats

	Social life and interpersonal relationship	— Disinterest in social dealings
	Marital life	— Self-initiated distance from siblings
	Self-care	— Hampered marital life
		— Careless behavior
		— Very unhygienic
2.Initial phase of CBT	Initial difficulty	— Initial difficulty in opting treatment
		— Least interested in treatment
		— Expecting transformation
	Initial recovery	— Gradual understanding of the treatment
		— Realistically felt positive effects
		— Improved physical health
		— Reduced symptoms of depression
		— Initial treatment found promising
		— Personally initiate conversation
		— Helped to relive
		— Medicine and therapy = effective
3.Middle Therapeutic Phase	Cognitions	— Changed opinion towards life
		— Adopted better thinking pattern
		— Feeling of completeness
		— Reduced anxious thoughts
		— Improved self-confidence
		— Control over negative thoughts
		— Reduced Fighting instincts
		— Flexibility
		— House hold work
		— Retrieved active behavior
	Behavioral	— Take care of self
		— Desire for daily walk habit
		— Tolerance
		— Enjoy dine in with family
		— Stay vigilant in apologizing
		— Controlled abusive behavior
		— Handle matters professionally
		— Enhanced independency
		— Enhanced calm attitude
		— Improved physical health
		— Improved appetite
		— Improved sleep
		— Desire to meet siblings
		— Reunion with old friends
		— Improved relationships with in laws
		— Reduced aggression towards siblings
		— Attention to children

Biological	— Increased likelihood for conversation
Social life and interpersonal relationships	— Healthy social interaction — Enjoy time with colleagues — Involvement in religious gathering — Determined to complete study — Improved concentration — Rejoined university — Regular job — Better performance at work
Academic performance	— Least desire to end life — Control over suicidal thoughts
Professional life	— Interested in remarriage — Better relationship with spouse
Suicidal ideation	— Derived out of hopelessness
Marital life	— Increased motivation — Enhanced encouragement
Experiencing therapy	— Best treatment so far — No harmful treatment

Pre-Therapeutic Phase

According to results, pre-therapeutic phase shows disturbance in cognitions, behavior, biological, social & interpersonal life and in marital life of patients with major depressive disorder. Such as aggression, insomnia, loss of appetite, loss of pleasure, self-induced isolation and negative thought process. Furthermore, they were having mood distortion, excessive mental pressure, usage of abusive language, excessive crying, constant headache, excessive feelings of regret, excessive fear, intense desire for suicide, agitation and recurrent thoughts, very unhygienic, developed negative thoughts, excessive anxious thoughts, chills and sweats, self-initiated distance from siblings. Further these symptoms would be clarified with verbatim of different patients.

*"I used to abuse which shows destructive behavior of the patient", "I used to cry a lot",
" I had constant headache," "I tended to live in isolation"," I used to think more negative "*

From the results, it was found that patients with major depressive disorder were suffering from terrible condition before the treatment. They had hampered life and they were facing destruction in all almost all aspects of their life.

Initial Effects of Cognitive Behavior Therapy

Result shows that initial effects of CBT were positive for patients. For instance, improved psychological health, feeling normal again, realistically felt positive effects, good understanding regarding treatment, very helpful, reduced symptoms of depression, initial treatment found promising and improved status of hypertension. Many participants found the therapy as a propitious treatment.

*"I realistically felt positive effect of CBT. No doubt it is effective ",
I have always good understanding of the therapy",
"This Therapy has reduced the symptoms of depression",
"this therapy was immensely helpful for me"*

Patients found CBT as pragmatic treatment. Remarks of patients show that they are recovering and their condition is getting better day by day through this therapy. Patients reported that now they were able enough to personally initiate the conversation. It helped them to relive and they are expecting great transformation with the aid of this treatment. However, one of the patient mentioned that effective results can be obtained from the combination of both medicine and therapy.

Middle Therapeutic Phase

While receiving cognitive behavior therapy, patients with major depressive disorder experienced enormous change in themselves. They explained how during this phase of treatment they shed off negative component and started adopting positive characteristics. They felt change in their behavior, such as tolerance, daily walk habit, controlled abusive language and violent behavior. (regained appetite, quality sleep achieved, controlled mood swings, improved attitude, improved physical activity, desired to start routine work, enjoy dine in with family, stay vigilant in apologizing, established control over negative thoughts, controlled abusive approach, controlled violent attitude, improved fighting instincts and control over irritation.

"it enhanced my tolerance level"

*," I started doing walk and exercise after receiving therapy to enhance my physical health",
 "I have achieved the quality sleep",
 "I have control over abusive language and as well as on violent behavior",
 "I regained appetite and got success in controlling the mood-swings"*

It shows that because of CBT patients experienced positive change in themselves. As CBT approach worked in progressive and in constructive manners. It has also efficiently altered the cognitions of patients with major depressive disorder. It altered thinking pattern in more rational manner and patients became logical towards life. It has facilitated in changing judgment towards life, and patients were able to adopt better thinking pattern. Application of cognitive behavior therapy has brought healthy impact on interpersonal relationships. Change in patient's attitude towards their siblings was clearly noticeable in results. Such as desire for meeting siblings. Another participant told the importance of relationship with in laws. In interview 9 she said. it has enabled her to pay attention to her children. Before treatment participants tend to isolate themselves from the outer world. But this therapy has fortunately brought massive change in attitude of participant towards socialization such as, likelihood for conversation has been improved, increased desire to visit friends. Now they show healthy social interaction, and enjoy time with colleague. Results also indicate that CBT helped patients to gain motivation to attend the university and other academic institutes. Now patients show involvement in professional activities, regular indulgence in professional life and better performance at work

*"It enhanced my self-confidence",
 I started actively participating in religious gathering",
 " I again joined my university"*

Perceived Effective and Ineffective Technique

Most of the participant found deep breathing, relaxation technique as an effective technique. Participant found therapy as a best technique because of sharing and counselling. One of the patient found activity to pen down negative thought as the most effective technique. Few participant found CBT as a problematic technique. Therapist should at least try to eliminate all the hindrance which are faced by patients during treatment-it was concluded that patient was not in favor of journal writing.

Results of the study seems to be partially similar with previous literature available. Most of the experiences resembles with the western researches and as well as show their relevance to Pakistani societal and medical set up. But some experiences seem to be quite different. Some prominent experiences narrated by patients with major depressive disorder were about initial indication of depression that is pre-therapeutic phase such as, increased aggression, loss of pleasure, insomnia, loss of appetite, agitation, mood distortion, self-induced isolation, hopelessness, negative thought process, abusive language, excessive crying, intense desire to suicide. Such symptoms of depression were also mentioned in the study of da Silva et al. (2018) such as exposure to violence, neglect and use of abusive language.

Initial symptoms of depression shared by the participants are in line with the study by purehsan and saed (2010) that patients of depression go through various conditions such as depressed mood, decreased pleasure and interest in almost every activity, sudden weight loss or weight gain. Moreover, lack of communication and recurrent thoughts of suicidal ideation.

Participants shared initial effect of cognitive behavior therapy for example some of the patients faced difficulty in opting for treatment. Results are in line with a study conducted by Ghaderi (2009) that portrayed how patient found difficulty in curing the disorder, they sometimes withdrew the session because at first, they did not find it effective against depression. Whereas, many of the patients found it very helpful. They have good understanding regarding treatment. Gau et al. (2012) narrated that CBT identify the individual strength and to modify the thinking pattern of the depression patient. And it does not only enhance thinking pattern but also clarify the process that mediate its effects. Results are similar to Kessler's study (2012) that illustrates that patients learned different skills to cope up with stressful life situation and they also learned to manage emotions via CBT. It helped them to relive, it gave relief from depression. One of the participant mentioned that desired effects are only possible through medicine and therapy. Purehsanand Saed (2010) also demonstrated that CBT along with anti-depressant not only lessened the depression symptoms but also had positive, useful and significant effect which lead to improvement in motivation.

Middle therapeutic phase in comparison to the pre-therapeutic phase showed physical and psychological changes in participants. Such pragmatic alteration is increased level of tolerance, quality sleep was achieved, improved physical activity, desired to start routine work, stay vigilant on apologizing, enjoy dine in with family. The results are in line with the study conducted by AasmaYousaf et al. (2020) that clients experienced change in themselves after going through the CBT. According to clients it helped to manage and control their depression as well as prevent them from relapsing. However, they learned different skills to cope up with stressful life situation.

Altered cognitions, changed attitude towards life, positive thinking style and enhanced self-confidence after five session of therapy are in line with Sachsenweger et al. (2015) that CBT helped to convert the irrational beliefs and thought process in to logical and rational thinking pattern.

Some of the positive results of CBT, expressed by participants were flexibility in behavior, regained interest in cooking, take interest in house chores, and take care of self, reduced idleness and desire for daily work habit. Such finding are similar to Sidman (2017) he found that CBT helps with shortcoming and flaws regarding behavior. First this therapy converted negative thoughts in to positive one which ultimately changed the behavior.

Participants also shared that they started taking interest in their professional life after treatment. Previous studies show that CBT not only eliminate the depression but it also enhances the professional life of patients of major depressive disorder (Warner et al., 2011).

Participants also shared that CBT had brought positive change their social life. Results of study are consistent with Kotianova et al. (2015) work that patients who did not participate dynamically in social activities, and preferred to live in isolation but after CBT. Results of the present study are also in line with Mohamadian (2018) work that patients who were treated with CBT, it helped them to recover from their psychological and social problems. Results are also consistent with Kotianova et al. (2015) study that patients with depression face difficulty in managing their relation, and CBT helped the clients and made them capable enough to find out the solution to resolve the marital conflicts, and they learned better way of communication with spouses.

The participants also believed that their personality was transformed due to CBT. It has enriched confidence and participants gained high self-value. Results are consistent with study conducted by Mohamadian (2018) that CBT helps to alleviate helplessness and improves self-confidence.

Most of the participants found breathing exercise and technique for relaxation as the promising one. Some of the patients found sharing and counseling as the best techniques. Other found pen down activity as the most effective. Results are in accordance with the study conducted by Warner et al. (2011) that relaxation technique improved the patient condition.

Results will help the clinical psychologists to identify the key problem areas, where specific techniques of CBT can be effectively used. The current study is qualitative in nature quantitative method can also be used on a larger sample for identifying the opinion and views of patients about the effectiveness of cognitive behavior therapy.

Conclusion

It is concluded that patients with major depressive disorder who are going through CBT experience enormous change in all aspect of their life. It brought tremendous positive change in patient's social and professional life, and this therapy not only brought massive progress in their interpersonal life and marital life but also reduced the recurrent thoughts of suicide and other symptoms of depression.

It can be manifested from the experiences of participants that cognitive behavior therapy is distinctly applicable on the patients with major depressive disorder. Therefore, considering importance of CBT for major depressive disorder patients, CBT should be provided prodigiously in all hospitals, organizations and medical sectors.

Acknowledgements

We are thankful to hospital administration for granting permission for data collection and patients for sharing their experiences.

References

- AasmaYousaf, RukhsanaKausar, &Iram Fatima. (2020). Cognitive behaviour therapy with compulsive hoarding: a single case study. *Journal Of The Pakistan Medical Association*, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.47391/jpma.1016>
- da Silva, S., Wiener, C., Ghisleni, G., Oses, J., Jansen, K., & Molina, M. et al. (2018). Effects of cognitive-behavioral therapy on neurotrophic factors in patients with major depressive disorder. *RevistaBrasileira De Psiquiatria*, 40(4), 361-366. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1516-4446-2017-2357>
- Gau, J., Stice, E., Rohde, P., & Seeley, J. (2012). Negative Life Events and Substance Use Moderate Cognitive Behavioral Adolescent Depression Prevention Intervention. *Cognitive Behaviour Therapy*, 41(3), 241-250. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16506073.2011.649781>
- Ghaderi, A. (2009). Cognitive Behavior Therapy and Eating Disorders. *Cognitive Behaviour Therapy*, 38(3), 191-191. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16506070802473239>
- Gold, C. (2015). Dose and effect in CBT for schizophrenia. *British Journal Of Psychiatry*, 207(3), 269-269. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.207.3.269>
- Jalal, B., Samir, S., & Hinton, D. (2017). Adaptation of CBT for Traumatized Egyptians: Examples from Culturally Adapted CBT (CA-CBT). *Cognitive And Behavioral Practice*, 24(1), 58-71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpra.2016.03.001>
- Kenardy, J., Robinson, S., &Dob, R. (2005). Cognitive Behaviour Therapy for Panic Disorder: Long-term Follow-up. *Cognitive Behaviour Therapy*, 34(2), 75-78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16506070410005410>

- Kessler, R. (2012). CBT by telephone for depression improved adherence compared with face-to-face CBT in primary care. *Annals Of Internal Medicine*, 157(6), JC3. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-157-6-201209180-02012>
- Kotianova, A., Slepceky, M., Vyskocilova, J., & Prasko, J. (2015). Experiential Techniques in the CBT Treatment of Personality Disorders. *European Psychiatry*, 30, 145. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0924-9338\(15\)30121-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0924-9338(15)30121-8)
- Lebedev, P., Garanin, A., & Paranina, E. (2021). Evolution of antihypertensive combined therapy: from depressin of academician A. L. Myasnikov to modern multi-component drugs. *"Arterial'NayaGipertenziya" ("Arterial Hypertension")*, 27(1), 73-82. <https://doi.org/10.18705/1607-419x-2021-27-1-73-82>
- Li, Y., Jing, B., & Han, Y. (2016). P4-348: Frequency-Dependent Changes in the Amplitude of Low-Frequency Fluctuations in Mild Cognitive Impairment with Depression. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 12, P1170-P1170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jalz.2016.07.092>
- Mohamadian, F., Bagheri, M., Hashemi, M., & Komeili Sani, H. (2018). The Effects of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on Depression and Anxiety among Patients with Thalassemia: a Randomized Controlled Trial. *Journal Of Caring Sciences*, 7(4), 219-224. <https://doi.org/10.15171/jcs.2018.033>
- Naeem, F., Gobbi, M., Ayub, M., & Kingdon, D. (2010). Psychologists experience of cognitive behaviour therapy in a developing country: a qualitative study from Pakistan. *International Journal of Mental Health Systems*, 4(1), 2
- purehsan, S., & saed, O. (2010). Effectiveness of cognitive-behavioral group therapy (CBGT) on reduction of social phobia. *Procedia - Social And Behavioral Sciences*, 5, 1694-1697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.07.348>
- Sachsenweger, M., Fletcher, R., & Clarke, D. (2015). Pessimism and Homework in CBT for Depression. *Journal Of Clinical Psychology*, 71(12), 1153-1172. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jclp.22227>
- Sidman, J. (2017). A Quantitative Assessment of an Alternative Anti-depression Therapy: Pilot Study. *Biomedical Journal Of Scientific & Technical Research*, 1(3). <https://doi.org/10.26717/bjstr.2017.01.000255>
- Soetrismo, S., Sulistyowati, S., Respati, S., & Nasrudin, M. (2017). EFFECT OF COGNITIVE BEHAVIORAL THERAPY FOR SEROTONIN LEVEL, DEPRESSION SCORE AND QUALITY OF LIFE IN CERVICAL CANCER PATIENTS. *Folia MedicalIndonesia*, 52(3), 231. <https://doi.org/10.20473/fmi.v52i3.5457>
- Stefan, S., & Hofmann, S. (2019). Integrating Metta Into CBT: How Loving Kindness and Compassion Meditation Can Enhance CBT for Treating Anxiety and Depression. *Clinical Psychology In Europe*, 1(3). <https://doi.org/10.32872/cpe.v1i3.32941>
- Warner, T., Nylander, S., & Whatling, C. (2011). Anti-platelet therapy: cyclo-oxygenase inhibition and the use of aspirin with particular regard to dual anti-platelet therapy. *British Journal Of Clinical Pharmacology*, 72(4), 619-633. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2125.2011.03943.x>
- Weitkamp, K., Klein, E., & Midgley, N. (2016). The Experience of Depression. *Global Qualitative Nursing Research*, 3, 233339361664954. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2333393616649548>
- Zagorski, N. (2019). Different CBT Formats Shown to Be as Effective as Individual CBT. *Psychiatric News*, 54(11). <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.pn.2019.5b21>
- Zauderer, C. (2012). The Lived Experience of Postpartum Depression in Orthodox Jewish Women. *Journal Of Depression & Anxiety*, 01(02). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2167-1044.1000112>

Author Information

Mobushira Zainab

Department of Psychology, Government College University Lahore, Lahore Pakistan

Syeda Shahida Batool

Professor, Department of Psychology, Government College University Lahore, Lahore Pakistan

Bareera Saeed (Corresponding Author)

Senior Lecturer, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, The University of Lahore, Lahore Pakistan

Hadiyya tur Rahman Mubaraka

Department of Psychology, Government College University Lahore, Lahore Pakistan

Mamoona Khan

Department of Psychology, Government College University Lahore, Lahore Pakistan
